

Enhancing a Competitive Advantage for Thailand's IT Entrepreneurs

Authors : T. Niracharapa, W. Angkana

Abstract : Since information and communication technology (ICT) plays a critical role in enhancing national competitiveness, it is a driving force for social and economic growth and prosperity. The ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) will integrate this into ASEAN countries as a new mechanism and a measure that will improve economic performance as a global economy. Government policies may support or impede such harmonization. This study was to investigate, analyze the status of Thai IT entrepreneurs and define key strategies to enhance their competitive advantage. Data were collected based on in-depth interviews, questionnaires, focus groups, seminars and fieldwork on information technology excluding communication. SWOT was used as a tool to analyze the study. The results of this study can be used to enable the government to guide policy, measures and strategies for creating a competitive advantage for Thailand's IT entrepreneurs in the global market.

Keywords : AEC, ASEAN, competitive advantage, IT entrepreneurs

Conference Title : ICCFMS 2014 : International Conference on Communication, Film and Media Sciences

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : May 26-27, 2014